

Examining a multi-layered approach for classification of Optical Character Recognition (OCR) quality without Ground Truth

In the past few decades, more and more heritage institutions have made their collections digitally available. At the same time, the availability of computer driven research tasks is increasing. With this combination, large data sets can be analysed in a fairly short time, something which would not be possible by hand. However, there is a pitfall; the OCR quality of digitised text is not always of high enough quality. This leads to several possible problems which can cause bias in the research results, both on the information retrieval and the analysis level. Although most researchers are aware of the presence of OCR errors, often they are not able to quantify these errors or the impact on their research. This leads to uncertainty about whether results can be published or not [3]. A measure for the (relative) quality of OCR would be very beneficial in the field of Digital Humanities. Furthermore, digital heritage institutions can use such a measure for improving their digitised collection.

For a few collections, a so called 'Ground Truth'-set is available. A Ground Truth set consist of digitised texts that are manually corrected by humans. Therefore, these digitised texts are of high quality and contain very few or no errors. They can be used to determine the quality of the corresponding OCR output. However, the creation of a Ground Truth set is time consuming and expensive, resulting in only a small amount of available Ground Truth sets. The above leads to the following question: *How can the quality of OCR-ed texts be determined when Ground Truth data is absent?*

This study examines a multi-layered approach for measuring the OCR quality of digitised texts without the presence of a Ground Truth. Previous research has mentioned a few possibilities, such as garbage detection [2, 4], lexicality, and confidence values from the OCR engine [1]. All of these measurements have problems with their accuracy due to the nature of texts. Therefore, we propose a multi-layered approach that combines various different measurements. We include statistical measurements, such as average sentence length, average word length and letter ratio. In addition, we include more complex measurements like the before mentioned garbage detection, language detection, and various approaches of dictionary look up.

If relevant, the time period or the category of a text are taken into account for the criteria of each measurement. Every measurement has its own weight, which determines how much it affects the outcome. After combining the outputs of the different measurements based on their weights, one categorical quality measure is suggested, such as 'weak', 'medium' or 'high' quality.

To substantiate our approach, we will use a data set for which we have the Ground Truth available. First, we measure the quality with the use of the Ground Truth. Then, we compare this result with the predicted quality measure from our proposed approach, and determine the precision and recall. Our approach will be tested on a collection of Dutch historical newspapers and books from the 17th century till the 20th century. The total set consist of ~36.000 newspapers articles and 2.055 book pages. Currently, we have implemented the first measurements and are testing various ways to validate the results.

References

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